

ATTITUDES TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AMONG STUDENTS IN NON-BOARD PROGRAMS: A MIXED-METHOD STUDY

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Attitudes towards English Language Learning among Students in Non-Board Programs: A Mixed-Method Study

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of non-board program students in their attitude towards learning English. In this mixed methods design the study used interviews for the qualitative phase, the researcher interviewed 5 non-board program students for focused group discussion and 5 non-board program students for in-depth interview and the quantitative data collected from 278 non-board program students from Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. In the quantitative part, the study employed adapted questionnaire. One statistical tool that was used to describe the level of the study's variable is mean. The study revealed that students have high level of attitude towards learning English which implies that students have positive attitude towards learning English. The data also shows that students have positive emotions towards learning English as they find learning English is worth it. Positive behavior towards English language learning were also reflected in the result as students were being active in learning the language. Moreover, positive cognition was also depicted in the result as students were able to apply English in real life situation as well as they are being aware in the usefulness of the language. In addition, the quantitative data mostly corroborated with the qualitative data.

Keywords: *attitude, english, cognitive, behavior, emotional, mixed-methods, convergent parallel design*

Introduction

Attitudes emerge as a significant concern in second or foreign language learning. One's reaction to a situation can vary, regardless of their preferences, the situation's quality, or the nature of the response (Yuliani et al., 2023). The concept of attitude can be examined from three different perspectives: behavioral, cognitive, and emotional. Each of these qualities plays a distinct role in determining language-attitude outcomes (Zuo et al., 2019). Attitudes in language learning reflect an individual's inclination towards the level of dedication they invest in acquiring a new language. Thus, the mindset of students plays a crucial role in their language learning journey, as it directly impacts their dedication to mastering the language. The mindset of students greatly influences their academic achievements (Zulfikar et al., 2019).

Therefore, possessing the ability to acquire English is crucial in the educational journey for students. However, the institution in Indonesia revealed that the students have negative attitudes towards English. Students are encountering challenges in learning English, particularly when it comes to speaking skills. The researcher also found that students faced difficulties in articulating their ideas in English during class. In short, most of the students stayed at the beginner and self-sufficient levels. The researcher found these results to be significant, leading them to believe that it was crucial to conduct an investigation into attitudes towards English learning. This investigation aimed to determine whether there was a correlation between students' attitudes towards the language and their level of English competence (Makhtuna, 2021).

In the Philippine educational system, English is not only taught as a subject but also used as the medium of instruction from elementary school through postsecondary education. Practicing is crucial for mastering the English language; however, some Students have bad attitudes because they find English difficult to learn as their second language. They often face challenges due to their proficiency in a different language or their native tongue. Fluency in English is not universal among Filipinos, even though it is taught in Philippine schools and is considered a second language. Recognizing the significance of having a strong education in English is undeniable. This is especially evident in the Philippines, where English is widely used as the primary language of communication in both workplaces and schools (Khastgir & Neogi, 2017).

The social value of this study is to investigate the importance of non-board program students' attitudes regarding English language learning, as it receives less attention in our own society and is not used more in classes. Furthermore, this study delves deeper into students' negative attitudes toward the English language and the causes for them. The predicted social value of students' views toward English language learning may be clearly justified in this study, which were provide immediate advantages to the research participants and society as a whole. This study aims to filter students' attitudes regarding English language learning in order to increase their enthusiasm in this academic subject through mixed-method research approach. To materialize this, the results of the study were presented to the students with the help of their instructors, administrators, and parents. Through this, it is hoped that initial actions can be made relevant to the result of the study. Furthermore, the completed paper is expected to be a helping hand to those students, teachers, and researchers who are conducting the same study.

Accordingly, the researcher observed that many studies have been conducted on attitudes towards the English language. However, most of these studies have been conducted in a global setting. To cite some, Alzamil (2019) conducted a study titled "The Effects of the Use of First Language on Learning English as a Second Language: Attitudes of Arabic EFL Learners," which is focused on the

students attitudes and the effects of their first language in learning the English language while Orfan (2020) conducted a study titled "Attitudes of Afghan Undergraduate Students Towards Learning English," it emphasizes how their attitudes have been affected by their access to the Internet and their English learning experience in English language centers. These studies, like the current study, emphasize the necessity of understanding language learners' attitudes and views in order to improve language learning results. The study, conducted in Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte, contributes to the existing body of knowledge by concentrating on non-board program students in a local college context. This study provides useful insights into the specific issues and viewpoints of this group of English language learners. On the other hand, this study stands out from the others that have been mentioned because it focuses on examining the perspectives of non-board programs students in a local college in Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. The study utilized a mixed-methods research approach to gather and analyze data. By examining the viewpoints of non-board program students on English language acquisition, this study aims to close the gap.

The dissemination plan aims to share the findings of a comprehensive research study that investigates attitudes towards the English language among students enrolled in non-board programs. The goal of this study is to assist researchers in better understanding the language learning experiences and barriers of this specific student demographic. This plan focuses on engaging targeted audiences, guaranteeing effective communication, and promoting meaningful action based on study findings. The study's findings helped educators and policymakers improve English language teaching and learning in non-board programs.

Research Questions

This study was look on the attitudes of non-board program students. Based on the background above, the researcher had formulated these research questions as follow:

1. What is the level of attitudes of non-board programs students towards English language?
2. What are the lived experiences of non-board program students with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning?
3. How do the non-board program students of KCAST cope with the challenges that they encountered with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning?
4. What insights can non-board program students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology share, with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning?
5. Do qualitative data corroborate with the quantitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative elements to offer a more thorough understanding of the research issue. Halcomb and Hickman (2015) state that integrating different methods is essential to preserve the credibility of mixed-methods research and can occur at any stage of the research process. This serves to offer a more thorough clarification of the research issue, the process of combining the qualitative and quantitative components is known as "mixing".

In this particular study, a mixed methods approach used, which combined quantitative and qualitative research methodologies. The qualitative phase involved in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with respondents to gather detailed insights into their experiences. Moreover, qualitative data allowed for a better comprehension of the underlying processes and the varying viewpoints of the respondents. On the other hand, the quantitative phase involved collecting numerical data of the participants through survey questionnaires in order to measure students' abilities. Furthermore, the quantitative data provided more objective measures, allowing for statistical analysis to identify the significance of the findings. This integration process known as "mixing" allowed for a more thorough analysis and interpretation of the data collected.

This research employed a convergent parallel mixed-method research design. In this approach, both types of data are gathered at the same time and given equal importance. The survey was conducted initially, then followed by either focus groups or individual interviews. The two data sets are evaluated separately, then merged, and the resulting combined findings are interpreted. This design is appropriate for the research because it aims to examine the likenesses, discrepancies, conflicts, or connections between the two sets of data (Hanson et al., 2005).

In the context of the study, a convergent parallel design was employed, strategically integrating quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis of attitudes towards English language learning. Data collection occurs simultaneously, utilizing both survey questionnaires and focus group discussions or interviews, ensuring a thorough exploration of the research topic. This design is particularly effective for examining the relationship between the two data sets, allowing the researcher to detect parallels, discrepancies, inconsistencies, and correlations between the quantitative and qualitative findings. By converging these data sources together, the study hopes to gain a more detailed and nuanced understanding of the research problem, resulting in a richer and more insightful analysis.

Moreover, the quantitative phase of this study employed a descriptive design. Describe the features of the population or phenomenon under study. This method collects quantifiable data for statistical analysis of population samples. This strategy aids in gathering

comprehensive and accurate data (McCombes, 2019).

In the context of the study, the descriptive approach seeks to provide an accurate description of the study's population, emphasizing its important characteristics while avoiding variable manipulation. The researcher was granted authorization to obtain a sample population from the good office of the registrar. The research study involved 278 participants who provided numeric data on complications, which were then analyzed using statistical tools like frequency, weighted mean, and standard deviation. To collect primary data, survey questionnaires were distributed to non-board program students who could provide extensive and reliable information. This design assists the researcher in ensuring that the data collected is dependable and can be used to make educated judgments or draw relevant conclusions from the study.

Alternatively, the qualitative stage of this research employed a phenomenological approach, a theoretical framework that enables educators to engage in adaptable activities to explore and understand complex phenomena like different aspects of human social interactions. It requires a deep understanding of the audience's beliefs and viewpoints regarding the subject being studied. Methods like focus group discussions and individual interviews were successfully employed for gathering qualitative data to understand community norms, complementing in-depth interviews, and deriving themes from the collected information (Alhazmi & Kaufmann, 2022).

In the context of the study, it enables the researcher to delve into the multifaceted experiences of individuals in a specific setting. The study sought a more in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon under examination by concentrating on participants' thoughts, perceptions, and lived experiences linked to the research issue. This method employed qualitative data gathering techniques like focus group discussions and individual interviews. The information was collected by conducting detailed interviews and group discussions with the participants. The interview guide contains questions given to five chosen individuals for the detailed interview and five individuals for the focus group discussion.

Participants

The main respondents of the study both in quantitative and qualitative strands are described in this section. The respondents are essential in conducting this study as they are the primary sources of data needed in this study. With them, the goal of the study was achieved and realized.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents in this study were non-board program students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in the second semester of S.Y. 2023-2024. They were chosen as respondents because the survey looked at students' attitudes regarding learning English in terms of language. Since the study claims to involve non-board program students at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology, it would be appropriate and valid for the respondents as it demonstrates their varied perspectives on learning English.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Program	Population	Sampling	Percentage
Bachelor of Public Administration	1007	72	1.87%
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	809	58	1.50%
Financial Management	121	9	0.22%
Human Resources Management	980	70	1.82%
Marketing Management	953	68	1.77%
Bachelor of Science in Office Administration	3870	278	7.18%
Total			

Furthermore, samples from a certain study population were selected using stratified random selection. The researcher divides the population into smaller groups based on similar characteristics using a method called stratified random sampling. Next, a random sample is selected from each stratum to create the final sample (Simkus, 2023). One of the study's common characteristics among the samples is their program, degree, or level of education.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in the non-board programs from all year levels. The institution has a total of (3870) non-board program students, consisting of (1007) Bachelor of Public Administration, (809) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Financial Management students, (121) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Management students, (980) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management students, and (953) Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students. However, the sample appropriate for the study is already computed by the statistician, which includes (72) out of (1007) Bachelor of Public Administration students, (58) out of (809) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Financial Management students, (9) out of (121) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Management students, (70) out of (980) Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management students, and (68) out of (953) Bachelor of Science in Office Administration students. In total, (278) students were sampled out of the (3870) students in the non-board programs.

Lastly, in selecting and choosing the qualified respondents in the study, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as the basis and guide

in the selection process. This includes: (1) must be enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in Non-Board Programs; (3) must be currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2023-2024) (4) must be male or female or any gender, and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, just like the quantitative phase, the participants were non-board program students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The selection of the participants was justified because the intended participants of the study are non-board program students. Thus, they are the only ones capable of providing authentic accounts about the research topic. These participants were included and involved in in-depth interviews and focus-group discussions. Specifically, the study was including 5 participants for the in-depth interview and another 5 participants for the focus group discussion.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

Assign Code	Sex	Year
IDI- 01	Female	1st year
IDI- 02	Female	4th year
IDI- 03	Female	3rd year
IDI- 04	Female	2nd year
IDI- 05	Female	4th year
FGD- 01	Male	2nd year
FGD- 02	Female	1st year
FGD- 03	Male	3rd year
FGD- 04	Female	2nd year
FGD- 05	Female	2nd year

Consequently, purposeful sampling was integrated. A purposive sample is chosen for a study based on the population's characteristics and the study's objectives. This method of sampling is highly beneficial when needing to quickly obtain a specific sample, without placing a major focus on representing proportions (Crossman, 2020).

Lastly, for the selection process, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as a basis. These includes: (1) must be enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in Non-Board Programs; (3) must be currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2023-2024) (4) must be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Instrument

In this section, the research tools for gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed.

Quantitative Phase

The researcher used a modified survey questionnaire on attitudes towards the English language, which was based on instruments created by Abidin et al. (2012).

Further, in a Five-point Likert Scale, participants were asked to rate each statement by their level of agreement on a close ended 5-level Likert scale with 4.30 – 5.00 very high, 3.50 – 4.20 high, 2.70 – 3.40 average, 1.90 – 2.60 low, 1.0 – 1.80 very low. Additionally, the Likert Scale is also useful for gauging concepts, attitudes, and sensations that are difficult for humans to perceive. The questionnaire was modified, but it was still validated by professionals. Following are the various methods, descriptions, and interpretations that were used to interpret how attitudes towards the English language was perceived.

Attitudes Towards English Language. The questionnaire for this variable was adapted from the study of Abidin et al. (2012). This tool is intended to determine the level of attitudes towards English language among non-board program students. It has 15 items distributed unevenly to three indicators: cognitive, behavioral and emotional.

Qualitative Phase

Regarding the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was developed by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who responded to the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, five were purposefully selected to undergo the IDI and another five for the FGD. Interviews were appropriate for obtaining knowledge, experiences, stories, views, and other pertinent data that could not be described in numerical terms.

During a research interview, a person known as the interviewer leads the conversation and poses questions, while another person known as the interviewee provides answers to those questions. Interviews can be done either in person or via phone calls. The internet is also becoming a tool for conducting interviews.

Procedure

For data collection, the researcher utilized a questionnaire to gather data from the sample. When obtaining the information, the researcher utilized the subsequent methods: The researcher gathered data using two primary tools, specifically a survey and a personal interview.

In the quantitative phase, a modified survey was used to assess the viewpoints of the students. The questionnaire was distributed after obtaining permission from the presidents of non-board programs at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Distributing the questionnaire typically requires 1-2 weeks, during which the researcher assists students in providing responses to each question item. Once all the students had answered the questions, the researcher proceeded to interview a few students to corroborate the questionnaire results. The results were added up, recorded, and analyzed to validate the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were conducted at the same time.

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview were conducted with the identified participants in order to gather the lived experiences of these non-board programs students with regard to their attitudes towards English language learning. Both the in-depth interview and the focus group discussion employed an interview guide. As a result, the researcher will have a documentary photo as proof that the interview has actually been done, which helped to confirm the validity of the choice (Creswell, 2012).

The discussion that occurred in the focus group focused on examining people's opinions, firsthand knowledge, worries, and aspirations surrounding the pertinent subjects. As per Tegan (2021), a focus group is a research technique that gathers a limited number of individuals in a controlled environment to respond to queries. The team is selected based on predetermined demographic characteristics, and the inquiries are crafted to provide insight into a subject of importance. The discussions take various forms, including face-to-face or online, but the researcher chose to have them face-to-face in order to fully understand the experiences and perceptions of the students.

Additionally, in-depth or one-on-one interviews were carried out to present an excellent chance to investigate how non-board program students view their attitudes toward learning the language. The researcher was conducted these interviews with ten (10) students that are specifically chosen. The in-depth interviews take place face-to-face in the classroom and run between 25 and 35 minutes.

Data Analysis

In this section, discussion covers the analysis of data, sequence, emphasis, and blending methods, as well as the step-by-step procedures, expected methodological challenges, study reliability, instrument validity, and ethical considerations when collecting quantitative and qualitative data from participants, informants, and respondents of the study.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative data analysis, the average responses of the respondents were evaluated using descriptive statistics like the mean. In-depth analysis was conducted using the survey data that was gathered. After the surveys were retrieved, the data were totaled and handled appropriately. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to perform additional descriptive and inferential statistical analysis on the survey data. These statistical analyses were used to determine how non-board programs students were doing.

In the study, the quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Here are the discussions to each of the statistical tool: (1) Mean was used to determine the level of attitudes towards English language learning among non-board program students, to answer research questions (2) Standard Deviation was used to measure how spread out the responses of the respondents are; (4) The survey data, which were collected, serving as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data were further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the level of non-board program students.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, the data collected during the conduct of the interview was analyzed that came up with conclusions that affirmed and supported the findings in the quantitative phase. As explained, the process of analyzing data in research entails condensing the large amount of gathered data and showcasing the findings in a manner that highlights the key aspects of the study (Harding, 2013).

In the study, data analysis was done after the process of transcribing the results of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion among the participants. The researcher analyzed the acquired data using coding and thematic analysis. Furthermore, when displaying and presenting the data, it was divided into categories based on similar responses from other individuals. The approach was known as thematic analysis.

According to the definition, thematic analysis involves examining and presenting the recurring themes found in a research study. As stated by Braun and Clarke (2013), thematic analysis is an adaptable approach to analyzing data employed by qualitative researchers in order to identify themes from interview data. This included analyzing the patterns and themes that arose from the responses or comments made by the participants/informants in the individual and group interviews. The themes were created to explore non-board program students' attitudes toward learning English through their lived experiences. The data were thoroughly examined to find and extract important themes that shed light on the research aims and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this setting.

To familiarize the data, the researcher listened to and transcribed the recordings of the participants' interviews and kept reading them over to identify similar answers. After familiarizing with the data, coding began, of which the researcher used coding to generate themes, ideas, and categories. Then, similar portions of text were labeled with a code so that they could be easily retrieved for further comparison and study.

Once the codes were grouped together, the researcher sorted the clusters according to the common meanings or connections among the codes. The following task was to assign names to the codes, which included utilizing the labels assigned to the theme and creating a comprehensive name that reflected the connection or significance associated with that specific theme.

At last, to ensure the data's reliability, the researcher consulted with her data analyst, an expert in the subject, and her research adviser for additional data verification. The researcher then presented the findings and interpretations of the data in tabular form for better understanding and exposition.

Ethical Considerations

The study gave top priority to the non-board program students' safety, anonymity, complete security, and secrecy in order to uphold their trust. In order to keep the participants' trust throughout the study, precautions were taken to make sure that these ethical issues are carefully addressed

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles, including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality, to ensure that ethical standards would be met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect, and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher was obtained permission from the participants and arrange the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence will not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

Throughout the course of my research, I developed a respectful and polite rapport with the participants and ask their permission to record the full conversation and all the responses of the participants before the interview starts. Additionally, I was maintained the secrecy of the in-depth interviews and the targeted group discussions while allowing the participants to ask me questions at any time. Participants will also have the option to decline to answer delicate questions. I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and courteous way by building connections with the participants and treating them nicely.

In this study, the principles of person respect were achieved through a variety of acts and procedures. From gaining informed consent to accommodating participants' schedules and assuring their grasp of the research processes and risks involved every effort was made to respect respondents' autonomy and rights. Building respectful connections with participants, obtaining permission before recording interviews, protecting the confidentiality of acquired data, and allowing persons to participate in the process all helped to create a respectful and ethical research environment. By valuing the respondents' well-being and dignity, the study was able to uphold the ethical principle of respect for persons and conduct research in a way that respected the autonomy and rights of the individuals involved.

Informed Consent is the foundation of ethical research (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). The phrase is made up of two crucial components, both of which need to be carefully thought about. This means that participants must be completely informed about the task requested of them, how their data were utilized, and any potential consequences that may arise. Participants must give clear, active, and signed permission to participate in the research, acknowledging their rights to access their data and the ability to withdraw at any time. The process of informed consent serves as the agreement between the researcher and the participants.

In the study, informed consent was achieved through sending the participants letters of permission and consent that included information on the study's methodologies, design, and procedures in order to assure the ethical conduct of the study. The goal of these letters is to explain the study's purpose to the participants so they can decide for themselves whether or not to join. Additionally, the researcher informed the participants that they have the right to ask questions during the interview and the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. Participants who opted out were given full permission to exit without having to give a reason and were given assurances that the information they provided was kept private. It is also the researcher's responsibility to inform the participants of the study's results. The researcher is able to guarantee that the study was carried out in a responsible and respectful manner by adhering to these ethical principles.

Beneficence as an ethical principle, it emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. The anonymity of the interviewees

is maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

In the study, beneficence was achieved by prioritizing the well-being and safety of participants. I protected participants' privacy by allowing them to respond anonymously and using pseudonyms. By doing this, I was able to guarantee the participants' interests and well-being and show that I am dedicated to ethical research practices.

Confidentiality was maintained for the data, results, and findings, as well as protecting the participants, through various methods. All private identities of the participants were concealed and remained undisclosed. Immediately after the analysis of the data, all materials such as audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and others must be removed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

In the study, the protection of participant confidentiality was achieved through a multifaceted approach that rigorously adhered to ethical and legal standards, including compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. I used discrete coding to denote each participant's response. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. I protected the identities and privacy of participants by using proper coding and other measures. Research data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Justice in the conduct of this study, the participants did not spend any amount during the interview. Non-board program students are the primary respondents of the study since it focuses on the attitudes of the students. Also, everyone considered respondents through the universal sampling to ensure just and unbiased treatment. The researcher provided them with meaningful tokens as a gesture of appreciation for their work on the research project. As the researcher, I am hoping that through this study, they were set into whatever negative experiences they had and maintain a good name into what positive contributions they could offer in this study. I ensured that only the participants' statements that pertain to the study's objectives are included in the information provided by them. Therefore, responses were accurately and correctly documented.

In the study, justice was achieved by employing universal sampling to select respondents, ensuring that all students had an equal chance of participating. As a token of appreciation for their cooperation and contributions, respondents received gifts or tokens of appreciation. During the study, the researcher gathered only information related to the attitudes of non-board program students relevant to the study's objectives. This method aimed to minimize any negative experiences participants might have encountered during the interview process and also to highlight their positive contribution to the research study. Furthermore, the accurate transcription of participants' responses ensured the integrity and reliability of the data collected.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phase. The first phase deals with the quantitative part in which it displays the status of non-board program students' attitudes towards English language learning and its variables which significantly predict the students' attitudes towards English language learning.

The second phase focuses on the qualitative aspect, which was displayed in a matrix format. The matrix displays how the participants have responded about their personal experiences with their students' attitudes towards learning English. Additionally, the matrix includes the examined problems, fundamental concepts, codes or categories, essential themes, and the underlying theoretical perspectives. Additionally, another matrix displays the data synthesis of the significant quantitative and qualitative results.

Level of Attitudes Towards English Language Learning

Presented in the table 2 is the level of attitudes towards English language learning of non-board program students across all year levels who were classified as students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. Also, the table presented the items that has the highest and the lowest mean rating in each indicator. Moreover, items on each indicator were given a description level from very high to low. On the other hand, each description was given an interpretation which depend upon the level on how non-board program students certainly manifested attitudes towards English language learning across all year levels. To support understanding, the study provided an overall illustration from a comprehensive examination based from data being collected from the participants.

Attitudes Towards English Language Learning. Shown in Table 2 is the level of the attitudes towards English language learning of non-board program students in Kapalong Agriculture of Sciences and Technology. It obtained an overall mean score of 3.92 with a description of high. This means that the non-board program students manifested oftentimes their attitudes towards English language learning. The variable of the study which is the attitudes towards English language learning integration which has 3 indicators namely: cognitive, behavioral, and emotional.

Cognitive. In terms of cognitive, the category mean is 4.21, which is describe as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, in item 1, I believe studying English is important because it will make me more educated got the highest mean of 4.44 which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the students. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants was the item 4, I like my English class so much; I look forward to studying more

English in the future with a mean of 3.88. This rating is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 2. *Level of Attitudes Towards English Language Learning*

No.	Item	Means	Description
A. Cognitive			
As a student, I...			
1.	believe studying English is important because it will make me more educated.	4.44	Very High
2.	think being good at English will help me study other subjects well.	4.36	Very High
3.	have more knowledge and more understanding when studying English.	4.16	High
4.	like my English class so much; I look forward to studying more English in the future.	3.88	High
5.	feel that studying English helps me get new information that I can link to my previous knowledge.	4.21	High
Category Mean		4.21	High
B. Behavioral			
As a student, I...			
1.	think speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried.	3.73	High
2.	ponder studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends.	3.49	High
3.	like to give opinions during English lessons.	3.58	High
4.	am able to make myself pay attention during studying English.	3.87	High
5.	hear a student in my class speaking English well, I like to practice speaking with him/her.	3.78	High
Category Mean		3.69	High
C. Emotional			
As a student, I...			
1.	feel proud when studying English language.	4.14	High
2.	feel excited when I communicate in English with others.	3.82	High
3.	don't get anxious when I have to answer a question in my English class.	3.58	High
4.	feel good when studying foreign languages like English is enjoyable.	3.88	High
5.	believe to be inquisitive makes me study English well.	3.86	High
Category Mean		3.86	High
Overall Mean		3.92	High

Behavioral. The behavioral was rated by the participants as high, with a category mean of 3.69. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. I am able to make myself pay attention during studying English garnered the highest rating with the mean 3.87, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Conversely, the item 2, I ponder studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends got the lowest mean of 3.49, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Emotional. The emotional got the category mean of 3.86, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. The item 1, I feel proud when studying English language got the highest mean of 4.14, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Meanwhile, item 3, I don't get anxious when I have to answer a question in my English class is the lowest rated item which has a high category mean of 3.58. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 4. Pseudonym of the Participants

Code	Pseudonym	Age	Gender	Course	Year Level
IDI 01	Ms. Eager	20	Female	BSBA-FM	1st Year
IDI 02	Ms. Compassionate	23	Female	BSBA-MM	4th Year
IDI 03	Ms. Concerned	21	Female	BSOA	3rd Year
IDI 04	Ms. Empowered	21	Female	BSBA-FM	2nd Year
IDI 05	Ms. Hopeful	22	Female	BPA	4th Year
FGD 01	Mr. Motivated	20	Male	BPA	2nd Year
FGD 02	Ms. Positive	19	Female	BSOA	1st Year
FGD 03	Mr. Supportive	23	Male	BSBA-MM	3rd Year
FGD 04	Ms. Calm	21	Female	BPA	2nd Year
FGD 05	Ms. Shy	21	Female	BSBA-HRM	2nd Year

Pseudonym of the Participants

Shown in Table 4 is the Pseudonym of participants. It can be gleaned in the table that the codes being used and the pseudonym in the focus group discussion and in-depth interview are being provided.

The five participants in in-depth interview were coded and given a pseudonym. The first participant was coded as IDI 01 with the pseudonym of Ms. Eager, during the interview she was very enthusiastic while answering the questions and it reflected on her actions and experience. The second participant coded as IDI 02 with the pseudonym Ms. Compassionate, because during the interview she feels empathy and concerned about her answers and she was suffering by that time. The third participant coded as IDI 03 with the pseudonym Ms. Concerned, as the interview was on going, she answered the questions in an attentive way it seems like she careful

observes and responsiveness. The fourth participant coded as IDI 04 with the pseudonym Ms. Empowered, because while answering the questions she was fluent and knowledgeable in her responses. The last participant for in-depth interview coded as IDI 05 with the pseudonym Ms. Hopeful, because she makes the situation more hopeful during the interview even though she was always having mistaken in her answers.

The five participants in focus group discussion were coded and given a pseudonym. The first participant coded as FGD 01 with pseudonym Mr. Motivated, because during the interview he is responsive or quick to answer in the conversation. The second participant coded as FGD 02 with the pseudonym Ms. Positive, because while she was answering the questions, she always thinks positive and have a smile on her face even she feels a little nervous. The third participant coded as FGD 03 with the pseudonym Mr. Supportive, because he always gives support and guide his self during the interview. The fourth participant coded as FGD 04 with the pseudonym Ms. Calm, because during the interview, she answered the questions calmly and collectedly and were just like having normal conversation all throughout the interview. Lastly, the fifth participant in focus group discussion coded as FGD 05 with the pseudonym Ms. Shy, because when she was answering the questions, her voice was too low and it's hard to hear her.

The Lived Experiences of Non-Board Programs Students with regard to their Attitude Towards English Language Learning

There are 4 essential themes which are created based from the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion of the participants on the first research question. Prior to revealing the findings of the interviews and discussions, the characteristics of the participants involved in gathering qualitative data are shown in table 4. The table displays the codes of participants' profiles for the qualitative phases.

Additionally, table 5 focuses on the firsthand experiences of non-board program students with regards to learning the English language. The key themes that were identified in the transcripts of the participants' answers to research question number one are encompassing themes that are outlined in the designated table.

Table 5. *The Lived Experiences of the Non-Board Program Students in displaying their Attitudes Towards English Language Learning*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Category</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Effects of Student's Attitude Towards English on their Learning	Being reluctant and not motivated to learn, seeing English as burdened Depending on the attitude of every day-to-day life Disliking English due to its difficulty and the feeling of pressure Fearing failure to construct ideas using the language. Lacking exposure to surroundings that help construct own ideas	Negative Perception and Effects on Learning English Lack of Confidence in Constructing Ideas in English	Experiencing Negative Attitude on Language Learning and Use	Affective Filter Hypothesis
Causes of Student's Difficulties in Learning English	Forcing themselves to learn in order to be knowledgeable about words in English. Struggling to pronounce and comprehend words properly. Experiencing less vocabulary leads to discouragement in learning Being unfamiliar with the terminologies affects comprehension and performance. Experiencing difficulties in learning because of a lack of knowledge about structure and grammar	Problems in Comprehending Words Properly Lack of Knowledge about the Structure and Terminologies of the Language.	Having Difficulty in Understanding and Using the Language Effectively	Saphir-Whorf Hypothesis/ Linguistic Theory
Effects of Learning English in the Emotion, Mental and Behavior of Students Towards the Language	Feeling happy and fulfilled while learning English, where students gain knowledge. A gratifying sense of worth derives from investing time and effort, leading to significant improvements. A satisfying and exciting feeling makes learning easier and challenging Experiencing a mental block while speaking in the class. Having a feeling of nervousness in oral recitations Being incapable of fully participating in English classes because of one's lack of English language proficiency	Worthwhile and Satisfaction Psychological Barrier Breakdown	Overcoming Psychological Barriers to Achieve Fulfillment and Satisfaction Encountering Difficulty in using the Language as Medium of Communication	Self-Efficacy Theory Sociocultural Theory

Effects of the Utilization of English Language in Medium of Communi-cation	Having trouble understanding English classes or topics and exhibiting a lack of cognitive involvement Finding it difficult to completely convey ideas and feelings when learning Being unable to effectively participate when requested to speak in English	Experiencing Trouble Catching Up in English Classes Having Difficulties Using English as the Only Instructional Language	and Instruction Classroom Participation
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Experiencing Negative Attitude on Language Learning and Use. This is one of the emerging themes from the response of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following codes negative perception and effects on learning English and lack of confidence in constructing ideas in English. Similarly, participants mentioned that since they had negative perception which results to a little understanding on the language. On the other hand, some participants also says that they are failure to construct ideas in English which also leads to being less confident in speaking English.

Negative perception and effects on learning English. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Student expressed common responses on English language learning in social and academic context. Most of them stated that learning English is difficult and burdensome, especially if they base it on their day-to-day lives. With that statement, participants are having difficulties grasping and learning the English language, especially in their field.

Similarly, Ms. Concerned recognized the English language as burdened because she is not motivated or interested when it comes to learning their lessons about English in academic context. This sentiment seems to be centered around of lack of motivation to learn English, possibly due to its perception that its burden. Learning a new language, in this case English, can be seen as a challenging task, which can lead to feelings of reluctance and lack of motivation. She stated that:

“Akoang attitude mag learn ug English is negative jud. Kay siguro dili ko hilig ug English so para sakoa negativeattitude akong mapagawas if maglearn ko ug English. Pero kadugayan mapaingon na siyag positive or belief nanakong magtoon for my own sake.” (IDI-03)

(My attitude towards learning English is really negative. Maybe because I am not interested in English, so my negative attitude comes out when I try to learn English. But eventually, it will turn into a positive attitude or belief that I want to learn for my own sake.)

Moreover, attitude plays a vital role in learning a new language. A positive attitude can make the learning process effective and enjoyable, while negative attitude can hinder progress. Incorporating English into daily life is a great way to enhance students learning. As what Mr. Supportive said that:

“Magdepende sa akoang attitude everyday kay like ma motivate ka karon and ugma dili na.” (FGD-03)

(It depends on my attitude every day, as sometimes I feel motivated and other times I do not.)

In addition, by making English part of the student’s everyday routine, they can improve their proficiency and make learning more natural and less of a chore. It might not be as hard, but students, based on their attitude, embody themselves if they want to pursue learning. Ms. Compassionate stated that:

“The difficulties in learning English, actually dili man jud siya ingon lisod jud if magbases lang ta for our day-today conversation. It’s just that ang Philippines man gud strict siya in terms of book context na English.” (IDI-02)

(The difficulties in learning English, actually it is not really difficult if we just base it on our day-to-day conversation. It is just that the Philippines is strict when it comes to English in a book context.)

Furthermore, Ms. Hopeful emphasizing the challenges and pressures associated with learning English, particularly in a classroom setting. English might be perceived as difficult for students because they are not motivated to learn. She stated that:

“My attitude affects my learning kay sakong nabal-an gud ayy, naa manay duha noh, positive or negative. Sa duha kay negative ko, because kay I find English man gud difficult na tun-an and dili sd ko ma motivate ug toon.” (IDI-05)

(My attitude affects my learning because, as far as I know, there are two possibilities: positive or negative. In my case, it is negative because I find English difficult to learn and I lack motivation to study.)

Lack of confidence in constructing ideas in English. This is the second code of the first probed issue. IDI and FGD participants imparted that they are not able to express themselves using and constructing English in a various context. This can be due to various factors such as limited vocabulary or fear of making mistakes.

Apparently, language proficiency can affect one’s ability to express oneself comprehensively. The difficulty of fully expressing ideas and emotions when learning is limited to using English as a means of communication can pose challenges for students in accurately conveying thoughts and feelings. Mr. Supportive said that:

“So, for me, kay the way nga naa kay makasugat na lain na tao, mag like American noh, dili man gyud nimo masulti or ma explain unsa imong pasabot.” (FGD-03)

(So, for me, you know, when you encounter someone different, like an American, you really cannot express or explain what you mean.)

Additionally, lack of exposure to an environment that facilitates the development of ideas and speaking skills in the English language. Students without sufficient opportunities to engage with English-speaking surroundings it can be challenging for them to develop fluency and proficiency in expressing one’s own thoughts and ideas. Ms. Eager stated that:

“As non-board program student, the toughest problem na akong na experience while ga learn ug naga study sa English is ma feel nako isolated ko ug lack of opportunities na maglearn. Lisod man gud if dli ka good sa English kay maglisod kag sabot. Ug kana ganing dili sad ka expose sa English-speaking environment na hawud mo English kay lisod kayo ma grasp ang language and to practice communication skills effectively.” (IDI-01)

(As a non-board program student, the toughest problem I have experienced while learning and studying English is feeling isolated and lacking opportunities to learn. It is really difficult if you are not good at English because understanding becomes challenging. And when you are not exposed to an English-speaking environment where people know to speak English, it is extremely hard to grasp the language and practice communication skills effectively)

Having Difficulty in Understanding and Using the Language Effectively. The second essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is having difficulty in understanding and using the language effectively with subcategories of problems in comprehending words properly and shortage of knowledge about the structure and terminologies of the language. Participants confirmed that they have struggling in comprehending words properly in learning English language as well as lack of knowledge about structure and grammar.

Problems in comprehending words properly. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Participants mentioned that they have problems in terms of comprehending words properly in English. Comprehension can be challenging to students, understanding words is essential for effective communication. In English, words carry meaning and convey different ideas or concepts.

With regard to that, using English really depends on how students express or comprehend the words that they have heard or read. Constraints on comprehending words properly may slow down students’ ability to learn. This factor can lead to students forcing themselves to learn about words in order to be knowledgeable about them, and it will be addressed by studying vocabulary, practicing reading and listening, and seeking opportunities to expand their knowledge of the English language. Ms. Calm said that:

“For me kay usahay malisodan ko sa English usahay labad siya sa ulo pero gina force nako akoang kaugalingon nga makat- onan jud siya.” (FGD-04)

(For me, kay, sometimes I struggle with English. Sometimes, it is difficult for me, and it can be frustrating, but I am determined to learn it.)

Furthermore, the cause of student’s difficulties is struggling to pronounce and comprehend words properly can make students can't deliberately speak using words properly, which affects their attitudes towards learning English. It emphasizes the importance of providing support and resources to help them overcome these challenges. Consequently, they are struggling since the language is hard to understand in terms of words. Ms. Concerned mentioned that:

“Ang thing na magka cause ug difficulties sa akoa maglearn ug English noh kay ang pronunciation kay sa English pronunciation man gud kay tricky kaayo siya, especially if ang mga sounds kay different sa akoang native na language na ginagamit.” (IDI-03)

(The thing that causes difficulties for me in learning English is pronunciation. English pronunciation can be very tricky, especially when the sounds are different from my native language that I am used to.)

Additionally, vocabulary is the foundation of effective communication. When students have a limited vocabulary, expressing themselves and understanding others can become challenging. A limited vocabulary can indeed lead to discouragement in the student's learning process, and it is one that causes them difficulties while learning the language. Mr. Supportive stated that:

“Para sa akoa kay, maglisod ko ug sabot then ang uban man gud sa English kay laglom ug mga language or words.” (FGD-03)

(For me, it is difficult to understand, and others English language or words are complex.)

Lack of knowledge about the structure and terminologies of the language. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants from IDI and FGD mentioned that the causes of students’ difficulties in having insufficient knowledge of the structure and terminologies of the English language are truly frustrating. Students having difficulties with higher-level English in their learning process.

Similarly, Ms. Empowered, encountering unfamiliar terminologies can be difficult for students to understand the content or context in which they are used. This can negatively impact students’ performance in tasks or assessments that require accurate comprehension. It’s important to actively work on expanding students’ vocabulary and familiarizing them with the terminologies specific to the field or subject they are studying. She stated that

“Especially during English, classes kay akoang ma ecounter jud nga difficulties nga magcause sa akong learning kay especially if naay mga English na terminologies nga wala ko kabalo ug lisod kaayo sabton. Unya kana, maka affect na siya sa akoang comprehension and overall performance.” (IDI-04)

(Especially during English classes, I encounter difficulties that can cause hindrance to my learning, especially if there are English terminologies that I am not familiar with and are difficult to understand. And that can affect my comprehension and overall performance.)

Moreover, English has a complex grammatical structure with various rules, tenses, and exceptions. Students struggle to understand some structures, leading to difficulties in English language learning. The structural complexity of English can pose challenges for learners in their learning process. As Ms. Hopeful said that:

“Ang reason na maglisod kog toon ug English kay dili ko motivated like kanang sa English diba or sa inyuha na mga education naa manang mga grammar rules or vocabulary ba diha, mga structure. Kana palang makabuang na maong cause ug difficulties nako na siya if maglearn kog English.” (IDI-05)

(The reason why I struggle to learn English is because I lack motivation, like the English in your education department, where there are grammar rules, vocabulary, and sentence structures. That alone can cause difficulties for me if I try to learn English.)

Overcoming Psychological Barriers to Achieve Fulfillment and Satisfaction. Another essential theme drawn from the responses of the participants is overcoming psychological barriers to achieve fulfillment and satisfaction with the following codes: worthwhile, satisfaction, and psychological barrier breakdown. Participants mentioned that to describe their feelings and negative barriers to learning English, which also become their attitude toward learning the language.

Worthwhile and satisfaction. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Many of the participants share the same experiences of the effects of learning English on their cognitive, behavioral, or emotional attitudes towards the language. Feeling worthwhile and satisfied in learning the language that they have finds value and a sense of fulfillment. They believed that it had a great impact on them towards learning the language, and it would boost their confidence as they became more proficient in English.

Similarly, students experiencing a sense of joy and satisfaction in the process of acquiring knowledge in the English language. When students feel happy while learning, it indicates that they have a positive attitude toward the learning process. This positive emotional state enhances their overall learning experience and motivates them to actively engage in language learning activities. Ms. Motivated mentioned that:

“Happy ko because it gives me fulfillment when it comes learning English kay tungod sakong pagtoon which is long term siya but sakong pagtoon sa English is that naka gain ko ug dako na knowledge when it comes in English.” (FGD-01)

(I am happy because learning English gives me fulfillment. It may be a long-term process, but through my English studies, I have gained a significant amount of knowledge in the English language.)

In addition, a satisfying sense of worth in giving effort and time leads to progress, which requires dedication and consistent effort over a period of time. They see that, English needs effort and time, and with that, they feel a deep satisfaction and sense of accomplishment, recognizing the value of their efforts and the resulting improvements in students. As Ms. Concerned said that:

“I feel that the amount of time and effort I invest in learning English is worthwhile. Kay worth it man siya makita man nimo ang improvement bisan ug taas pang time ug effort na na kalas. Sa tinod-anay lang jud noh learning a language requires dedication and practice man jud, maong always natong e value ang kana na time ug suliton sa pagtoon aron makita jud ang agi.” (IDI-03)

(I feel that the amount of time and effort I invest in learning English is worthwhile. It is worth it because you can see the improvement even with the long hours and effort invested. In reality, learning a language requires dedication and consistent practice, so we should always value the time and effort spent in learning to truly see progress.)

Additionally, Ms. Eager emphasizes the effects of emotional and behavioral attitudes on students, saying that they feel excited and make learning easier for the reason that they see learning English as rewarding and challenging in their learning process, and with that, they acknowledge their attitude in regards to English. She stated that:

“The amount of time ug effort na akoang gi invest in learning English, I think, both siya rewarding ug challenging sa akoo. Kay ug porsigido gyud ko mutoon, gahinan mn jud nako na ug time. Naka try namn sab ko maglearn ug English, dili sab dali but challenging siya noon.” (IDI-01)

(The amount of time and effort I have invested in learning English, I think, has been both rewarding and challenging for me. Because if I am determined to learn, I have to allocate a significant amount of time. I have also tried to learn English before, and it was not easy but rather challenging.)

Psychological barrier breakdown. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. Participants consider barriers can cause students low self-esteem when learning the language. The experience of a of a psychological breakdown means that they face emotional or

mental obstacles that hinder their progress in acquiring English language skills. This negative leads students to bad results if it cannot be addressed.

Similarly, mental block is one of the factors contributing to students learning involvement. This negative attitude can hamper students learning process for the reason that they are temporarily unable to think clearly or express themselves effectively during oral communication. This barrier can lead to difficulties in finding the right words, organizing thoughts, or articulating ideas coherently. As Ms. Compassionate mentioned that:

“So, my unforgettable experiences nga nag affect sakong attitude is when, nag debate, like naa tanang ideas but because kanang, sakong geingon gaina diba na ma mental block. Tungod sa mental block, akoang mga idea, is dili nanako magawas kay tungod lagi nakulbaan, nagkurog nang tingog so mao na nga problem sa mga student is mental block.” (IDI-02)

(So, one of my unforgettable experiences that affected my attitude is when I participated in a debate. I had many ideas, but because of a mental block, I could not express them. Due to the mental block, my ideas could not come out because I was nervous and my voice was shaking. This is a common problem among students, the mental block.)

Additionally, feeling nervous during oral recitations is one of the weaknesses of students in class participation. The pressure to perform well or to be evaluated by peers and teachers can contribute to feelings of nervousness. Nervousness can also arise from a lack of confidence in one’s speaking ability. To address this, there are strategies that can help manage nervousness during oral recitations. Ms. Positive affirmed that:

“My experience is yong nerbyos pagtawagin ka or even wrong grammar, nawawala ka sa isip, parang blanko ang pag-iisip mo, parang ganun.” (FGD-02)

(My experience is that when I am called upon or make a grammar mistake, my mind goes blank. It is like my thoughts disappear and my mind becomes empty, something like that.)

Encountering Difficulty in using the Language as Medium of Communication and Instruction Classroom Participation. This is the fourth essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants with codes/categories which are experiencing trouble in catching up in English classes and having difficulties using English as the only instructional language. Participants confirmed they have difficulties in using the language in communication.

Experiencing trouble in catching up in English classes. This is the first code for the fourth probed issue. The participants encountering difficulty in using English in communicating with other people or in classroom setting. Instructors or teachers letting them to speak in the class in order to have effective communication with their peers or classmates.

Similarly, Ms. Eager recognizes that it is difficult to communicate fully while speaking English. Students with limited vocabulary can find it challenging to express themselves fully in English. When students lack the necessary words to convey their thoughts and ideas, they may struggle to communicate their intended message effectively. Building vocabulary through reading, listening, and actively learning new words can help expand communication abilities. She stated that:

“The unforgettable experience na akong na experience kay katong naay oral recitation, uso mn jud samong mga instructors magpa oral noh. So, amoang instructor po nag require na mag answer me through English kay para daw ma enhance amoang English pronunciati on ug communication skills. So, kana na time is naolaw ko since nitubag ko sa oral sir but dili English halos noon Bisaya so ayon narealized nako na importante sad maglearn ug English, bisan dili ka major in English.” (IDI-01)

(The unforgettable experience I had was during an oral recitation, as our instructors often conduct oral exercises. Our instructor required us to answer in English to enhance our English pronunciation and communication skills. At that time, I felt embarrassed because I responded orally, but not in English, mostly in Bisaya. That is when I realized the importance of learning English, even if it is not your major.)

In addition, being incapable of fully participating in English classes can disrupt students learning. A lack of English proficiency can make it difficult to fully comprehend the content and instructions provided in English classes. Understanding the lessons, reading, and discussions may be challenging, which can hinder students’ active participation. Ms. Empowered said that:

“So, as a non-board student, di jud mi proficient or competent sa English language as non-board student. So, kana if amoang instructor during English class kay magpa oral recitation unya mag ask siyag question in English, somehow lisod sa amoa nga ma express amoang ideas in speaking English.” (IDI-04)

(So, as non-board students, we are not really proficient or competent in the English language. So, when our instructor during English class conducts oral recitations and asks questions in English, it is somewhat difficult for us to express our ideas in spoken English.)

Having difficulties using English as the only instructional language. This is the second code for the four probed issues. Participants from IDI and FGD affirmed that using English as the sole instructional language can be challenging for students who have limited proficiency in the language. Understanding complex concepts, following instructions, and engaging in discussions can be difficult when English is not yet fully mastered. Struggling to comprehend the content being taught is a reason why some instructors use English

for a long period of time. With that, students will not be able to understand what is being taught, and it is really difficult to express their ideas.

In the sense that, students from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds may face challenges in conveying their ideas and feelings in English. A classroom environment where English teachers only speak English during lessons can pose challenges for students who are still developing their language skills. This was involve actively seeking clarification and engaging in discussions to practice expressing them ideas and feelings. As Mr. Supportive affirmed that:

“Sa akin ay, yung experience ko kay tinanong ako sa research naming sa panelist na hindi ako nakasagot in English.” (FGD-03)

(For me, the experience was when I was asked by the panelists in our research presentation and I could not respond in English.)

The Coping Mechanism of Non-Board Programs Students with regards to their Attitude Towards English Language Learning

Displayed in Table 6 are the responses of the participants in regards to their coping mechanisms in English language learning. Five essential themes were identified through the in-depth analysis and focus group discussion of participants in response to the second question. The fundamental subjects included codes derived from the topics being investigated, which are outlined in the table.

Table 6. *The Coping Mechanisms of the Non-Board programs Students with the Challenges in related to their Attitudes Towards Learning English*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/Category</i>	<i>Essential Theme</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Effects of Employing Diverse Alternative Strategies and Various English Learning Resources	Reading different books and watching videos related to English for developing a positive attitude	Language Proficiency Dashboard	Applying Various Techniques to Discover and Improve Language Learning and Use	Theory of Multiple Intelligences
	Connecting interest in reading books, news, and dictionaries to build proficiency in the language.	Utilizing Various Materials	Promoting Effective Collaboration with others while Learning	Sociocultural Theory
	Analyzing one's mistake to learn from it and think positively.			
	Discovering interesting materials to shape attitudes in learning	Promoting Effective Collaboration with others while Learning	Promoting Effective Collaboration and Social Learning	
Effects of Teamwork on Changing Attitudes	Exposing oneself to engaging activities for enhancing English proficiency	Seeking a Collaborative Approach to Language Learning	Cultivating Optimism for Lifelong Language Learning and Proficiency	Positive Psychology Theory
	Asking for help from the teacher or a fellow student			
Effects of Positive Attitudes in the Learning Process	Valuing the importance of seeking support from peers and friends	Creating a Positive Attitude for Enhancing One's Language Learning	Empowering Learning Through Customized Interactive Resources	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework
	Seeking assistance and support from classmates or relatives who are experts in English terminologies			
Impacts of Support or Resources on Attitude and Learning	Collaborating with one's colleagues	Developing an Optimistic Mindset for ongoing English Learning	Empowering Learning Through Customized Interactive Resources	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework
	Boosting confidence through positive attitude			
	Using English regularly for improving a good attitude			
	Staying calm and having more patience fosters willingness to learn.			
Impacts of Support or Resources on Attitude and Learning	Considering positive attitudes as motivation in the development of English competency	Interactive learning Resources	Empowering Learning Through Customized Interactive Resources	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework
	Building a positive attitude helps one understand concepts while honing language learning skills.			
	Using websites or applications that ignite the learning leads to improved understanding of English.			
	Investing time and effort in exposing oneself to documentaries or videos that use English for clarification of understanding			
Impacts of Support or Resources on Attitude and Learning	Finding helpful language learning apps and websites to support learning needs	Personalized Learning Paths	Empowering Learning Through Customized Interactive Resources	Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework
	Acquiring knowledge using Google and other resources to cultivate optimistic outlooks			

Applying Various Techniques to Discover and Improve Language Learning and Use. This is one of the essential themes from the response of the participants during in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the following codes such as, language proficiency dashboard and utilizing various materials. Similarly, participants mentioned that since they suggest techniques to cope up with challenges in learning the language.

Language proficiency dashboard. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Participants from IDI and FGD stated that the language proficiency dashboard allows them to track or monitor language proficiency while learning the language. Through this code, they will be able to help them learn the language and enhance their positive attitude.

In that sense, it is highly beneficial for students to read books to improve their positive attitude. With this, students allow themselves to explore different ideas, perspectives, and experiences, which can broaden their horizons towards learning the English language. Ms. Compassionate stated that:

“Basa kag mga books, kundi mag tan-aw or maminaw kag mga, American news or programs. Since English naman gud na siya, bali mas dali mo adapt atoaang mind once madungog or makita, unlike lang sa kanang itudlo. Yes, maka learn man jud kag itudlo pero mas effective man gyud nang ikaw mangita sa imong way kay sa magbase lang ka sa uban kay lahi-lahi man gud tag mga learning techniques. Naay learning techniques nga mogana sa akoa pero dili mogana sa imoha. And, likewise naa poy mogana sa imoha na dili mogana sa akoa.” (IDI-02)

(Read books, but also watch or listen to American news or programs. Since English is already familiar to you, it is easier for your mind to adapt when you hear or see it, unlike just being taught. Yes, you can learn from being taught, but it is more effective when you find your own way because we all have different learning techniques. There are learning techniques that work for me but may not work for you. And likewise, there are techniques that work for you that may not work for me.)

In connection, Mr. motivated himself by recognizing the importance of employing diverse alternative strategies and various resources. One of those is watching videos that relate to English. Students find it meaningful to watch different videos that could help them learn English. Especially if the videos have a subtitle that can introduce new words and help people understand English. He said that:

“Basa-basa lang ug kanang mga dictionaries, chart books like that, and also watching documentaries like that.” (FGD-01)

(Just keep reading dictionaries, chart books like that, and also watching documentaries like that.)

Additionally, one strategy that students can apply in their learning process, especially in grammar, is analyzing their own mistakes in order to learn from them. By acknowledging mistakes, students will be motivated to continue learning. Ms. Empowered stated that:

“So, as non-board student, di man gyud ta specialize ana nga field which is English, so, open jud ta sa mga kamalian like sa atoaang grammar, so akoa lang na siyang gina take positively gina serve nako siya as inspiration na ma motivate sako to continue learning especially in English language.” (IDI-04)

(So, as a non-board student, you know, we do not really specialize in that field, which is English. So, we are open to making mistakes, especially in our grammar. But I take that positively and use it as inspiration to motivate myself to continue learning, especially in the English language.)

Utilizing various materials. This is the second code of the fifth probed issue.

The participants imparted that students need to utilize various materials, such as engaging activities, interesting materials, and different methods. With this, students keep the learning process interesting and cater to their different learning styles.

Similarly, Ms. Concerned is interested in discovering interesting materials that can shape their attitude towards learning the English language. Engaging and captivating materials can make their learning more enjoyable and help them cultivate a positive attitude towards learning. She stated that:

“Ang technique na ma employed to foster a positive attitude kay I will “find interesting materials” kay ug mangita kag materials na imohang gamiton sa pagfoster sa imong positive attitude maybe ma improve sad imong English skills ana. Ang materials na nakita nako sauna is una jud nako gi consider is nangita ko for English materials na ma align sa akoang interests, like as books, or movies mga naay mga subtitle, or podcasts I think kablo man ta anag podcats noh. Mas nindot man pod ug interested ka maglearn kay magbetter jud ka.” (IDI-03)

(The technique that can be employed to foster a positive attitude is to “find interesting materials”. If you search for materials that you can use to foster your positive attitude, it may also improve your English skills. The materials that I previously found and considered were English materials that align with my interests, such as books, movies with subtitles, or podcasts. I believe we can aslo learn a lot from podcasts. It is even better if you are interested in learning because you will definitely improve.)

In addition, utilizing various materials can impact students learning, especially if they are exposed to engaging activities to enhance their language proficiency. In this way, students improve their language skills and understanding of natural English conversations. As Ms. Empowered mentioned that:

“Akong e-expose akoang sarili sa mga engaging activities nga ma enhance akoang English proficiency.” (IDI-04)

(I will expose myself to engaging activities that can enhance my English proficiency.)

Promoting Effective Collaboration and Social Learning. The second emerging theme drawn from the responses of the participants is the promoting effective collaboration with peers and English instructors while learning and seeking a collaborative approach to language learning. Participants mentioned that, they are seeking assistance from the classmates and instructors in order to have better understanding of the language.

Promoting effective collaboration with others while learning. This is the first code for the second probed issue. When learning in an academic context, especially in the modern world, students need collaboration with peers and instructors for effective learning, where instructors will be able to explain concepts or content for students understanding.

Similarly, effective collaboration between students and instructors is good since teachers catered to the needs of students learning. Reaching out to an English teacher and asking for assistance is a great strategy for improving English proficiency. As Mr. Supportive said that:

“Para sa akong magtutulong sa akong ate kay teacher man akoang ate ug unsaon pag pronounce.” (FGD-03)

(For me, I will ask my older sister since she is a teacher on how to pronounce.)

Additionally, students seeking clarification from the teacher in English terms or concepts where they are confused. It is important for instructors to give explanations and examples to be able to understand terms and concepts. This factor hinders students for the reason that they will have a hard time understanding the terms or concepts. As Ms. Calm confirmed that:

“Sa akong magtutulong sa akong magtutulong rako sakong ig-agaw once naa koy malibogan kay teacher man pod siya.” (FGD-04)

(For me, I will seek assistance from my cousin to teach me because I am confused because she is a teacher.)

In connection, Ms. Empowered values and recognizes the importance of collaborating with their peers and friends to support their learning process in the English language, especially in learning basic English. In this context, students find learning easier if they collaborate with others who are specialized in that language. She stated that:

“Akong gina consider na support kay, collaboration with my peers and friends na hawud mo English, and of course sa resources naman kay mga books, mga movies na naga utilize ug English language nga makakuha pod sakoang interest to learn.” (IDI-04)

(I am considering support for collaboration with my peers and friends who are fluent in English, and of course, the resources such as books and movies that utilize the English language, which also pique my interest to learn.)

Seeking a collaborative approach to language learning. This is the second code for the first probed issue. Participants have mentioned that having a collaborative approach to language learning will improve English proficiency and master English in a way that they have partners to collaborate with towards learning the English language in their field.

In that sense, seeking support from experts or collaborating with colleagues to enhance a positive attitude. If students are with someone to learn with, they are motivated and inspired to learn, and they will quickly grasp the English language, especially using it in class discussions. As Ms. Hopeful said that:

“Kaming mga non-board or ako isa ana ang nakita nakong makatabang sako maglearn or sa akoang observation is nice ug naa kay kauban or partner na hawud about sa English like conversation partners na same mo naga exchange ug words and siya akoang mamahimong resources para ma develops akong positive attitude.” (IDI-05)

(For us non-board or me personally, what I have observed and found helpful in my learning is having someone with me, like a partner or companion, who is fluent in English. We can engage in conversations and exchange words, and they can also serve as my resource to develop a positive attitude.)

Cultivating Optimism for lifelong Language Learning and Proficiency. This is the third essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants with subcategory of creating a positive vision for enhancing one’s learning attitude and developing an optimistic mindset for ongoing English Learning. Participants confirmed that they have difficulties learning the language, so to cope with this, they need to enhance their learning and have a good mindset when learning the English language in order to improve better at utilizing the language.

Creating a positive attitude for enhancing one’s language learning. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants stated that having a positive vision for enhancing their attitude towards English is helping them boost their confidence, willingness, and motivation to practice the language regularly. The majority of the participants emphasized these attitudes.

Similarly, Ms. Concerned stated that through a positive attitude, students boost their confidence in every aspect of English. Allowing themselves to speak up and effectively communicate with others. She said that:

“Ang ways na maka help ug improve sakong positive attitude kay e boost nakog maayo akoang “Confidence” kay having a positive attitude man gud kay maka boosts sa students' ug confidence in using English. So kani akoang confidence ma allows akoang kaugalingon mo to take risks, speak up, and engage in conversations, which is maka leads ug improvement sa speaking and communication skills.” (IDI-03)

(The ways that can help improve my positive attitude is by boosting my confidence well because having a positive attitude boosts students' confidence in using English. So, this confidence allows me to take risks, speak up, and engage in conversations, which leads to improvement in speaking and communication skills.)

Additionally, the effects of a positive attitude in the learning process are that students are motivated to practice and used English regularly as they want to cultivate a positive attitude towards English language learning. Ms. Compassionate said that:

“So, in what ways do positive attitudes help me to improve my English is by conversing day by day, using my work. I work in a call center of VPO, so makakoan jud ka na ang work field nako is in English talaga. Unlike, sa uban nay Spanish pero English akoang gikuha kay mao raman pod nay part time since I am a student to support my tuition, my expenses here, so na improve siya tungod lang sa kanang, dili sa pangpangoan ha, pero na improve, ma improve once imong ginagamit siya daily.” (IDI-02)

(So, in what ways do positive attitudes help me to improve my English? One way is by conversing day by day, using it in my work. I work in a call center of a BPO, so you can really say that my work field is in English. Unlike others who may speak Spanish, I chose English because it is also my part-time job as a student to support my tuition and expenses here. So, it improves because of constant usage, not just for show, but it really improves when you use it daily.)

Moreover, the willingness to learn is really important in English. Students should stay calm and have more patience to learn English, seeing that it is a difficult language to learn, especially if they use it in various contexts. Ms. Eager stated that:

“To overcome any negative attitudes towards learning in English, is maybe mag focus on building confidence through mag sigeg practice ug speak ug English and hatagan jud ug time para makatoon.” (IDI-01)

(To overcome any negative attitudes towards learning English, maybe focus on building confidence through continuous practice and speaking in English, and really allotting time to learn.)

Developing an optimistic mindset for ongoing English learning. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participants shared that the optimistic mindset they used was building positive attitudes, controlling stress or struggles, and using a positive attitude as motivation. These ideas help students understand concepts and terminologies in English and lessen their struggles in learning.

Similarly, Ms. Empowered mentioned that the positive attitude contributes to students’ overall performance in learning the language. Building a positive attitude can help students easily understand concepts in English. A positive attitude fosters an openness to learning and a willingness to explore new concepts. She stated that:

“Those positive attitudes help me improve my English language skills in a way that naga serve siya sako as motivation to learn of course naga contribute siya sa akoo ug eagerness to continue my development especially in my English competency po.” (IDI-04)

(Those positive attitudes help me improve my English language skills in a way that it serves as my motivation to learn, of course, it contributes to my eagerness to continue my development, especially in my English competency.)

To add, Ms. Hopeful expresses that by controlling stress or struggles, they are able to manage and overcome the stress and difficulties they encounter while learning English. They also develop a more optimistic attitude that contributes to students’ motivation, eagerness to continue their development, and overall improvement in their English language skills. She said that:

“Sa katong negative pako mo learn ug English, kay murag lisod jud ikat-on promise. Pero now positive ko and I can say na ang positive attitude is maka help sya sa paglearn ug English kay mabawasan imong pagka stress or struggle kay ug positive ka maglearn maybe willing jud kaayo ka mo learn or eager kaayo ka mo learn.” (IDI-05)

(When I was still negative in learning English, it seemed really difficult to learn, I promise. But now, I am positive and I can say that a positive attitude can help in learning English because it reduces your stress or struggles. If you have a positive mindset, you become more willing and eager to learn.)

Empowering Learning Through Customized Interactive Resources. This is the fourth essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants to subcategory interactive learning resources and personalized learning paths. Participants confirmed that they utilize apps or platforms to integrate their learning.

Interactive learning resources. This is the first code of the fourth probed issue. Learning resources are educational materials or tools that actively engage learners in the learning process through hands-on activities or multimedia when learning the English language. With this, students are able to give time and effort to engage in different interactive learning resources.

Apparently, using websites or applications that ignite learning can definitely lead to improved understanding of English. These interactive websites or applications are designed to enhance English language skills, specifically reading, writing, listening, and speaking abilities in English. Ms. Eager mentioned that:

“Ako usa ka non-board program students, ilabina nga gikan sa BPA program. We find helpful resources and support para maka develop ug positive attitude is kanang mga application sad or websites na maka help sa akoo ug learn sa English.” (IDI-01)

(I am a non-board program student, especially coming from the BPA program. We find helpful resources and support to develop a positive attitude, such as those applications and websites that can help me learn English.)

In connection, learning is continuous; students invest time and effort in exposing themselves to documentaries or videos for effective

learning. It is their coping mechanism to overcome learning difficulties because English is difficult. They watch videos for clarification and apply to themselves what students learn from them. Ms. Calm said that:

“Dili isipon na dili nimo siya kaya tun-an then magtan-aw lang ug mga movie gani na kanang English tapos imohang pong e practice sa imohang kaugalingon.” (FGD-04)

(Do not think that you cannot learn it, then just watch movies in English and practice it on your own.)

Personalized learning paths. This is the second code for the fourth probed issue. Participants from IDI and FGD shared that they can acquire the English language through personalized learning paths that include helpful resources, support, and self- support, and self- appreciation, which have greatly impacted their learning of English.

In that sense, acquiring the English language is difficult, but students find helpful websites like Google to help them have a better understanding of and an optimistic outlook towards the language. Mr. Motivated stated that:

“In my perception, nagakoan lang ko sa google it is because we all know that in Google, there are so many information.” (FGD-01)

(In my perception, I just rely on Google because we all know that in Google, there is a lot of information available.)

To add, engaging in social media presence can actively help students immerse themselves in authentic English language usage and gain exposure to different accents, expressions, and vocabulary. It involves language learning apps, includes interactive lessons, vocabulary exercises, or games that focus on enhancing learning in the language and making the learning engaging. As Ms. Concerned stated that:

“Kablo man jud ko na sikat kayo ang social media or websites noh so ahhhhh siguroo, ang resources na akong ma find out or helpful sa akoo as non-board program kay katong mga “Language learning apps and websites” Kani siya na mga platforms man gud kay maka provide siyag interactive lessons, vocabulary exercises, or mga games na focuses sa vocabulary na which importante sad ug ang language practice opportunities kay koan kanang that make learning English more engaging and enjoyable siya.” (IDI-03)

(I know that social media or websites are popular. So, the resources that I can find helpful as a non-board program student are the language learning apps and websites. These platforms provide interactive lessons, vocabulary exercises, and games that focus on vocabulary, which are important. They also provide language practice opportunities that make learning English more engaging and enjoyable.)

The Insights shared by Non-Board Program Students as regards to their Attitude Towards English Language Learning

There were three essential themes which were drawn from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table. It also talks about the insights that can be shared by non-board program students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology with regards to their attitude towards learning mathematics in their cognitive, behavioral and emotional aspect.

Table 7. *The Insights Shared by Non-Board Program Students with regards to their Attitudes Towards Learning English*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Category</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Impact of English Language Proficiency on the Learning Process in Cultivating Understanding	Finding it difficult to understand English concepts, but striving to improve with time and effort Considering it as the second language in the medium of communication Gaining proficiency in English can lead to numerous opportunities. understanding Learning English is very difficult most of the time, especially when using it in communication Giving time and effort since English is burdened with cultivating one's Valuing the importance of learning	Struggles with Communication in the Learning Process Language Practice with Time and Effort English Proficiency for Better Opportunities	Learning English Language Takes Time and Effort Exposure to Language Use Enhance One's Learning Constant Practice using the Language Makes One Proficient in Language Use	Input Hypothesis
Effects of Different Language Learning Methods for Acquiring English Language Skills in Various Contexts.	English for having better opportunities Using the language for communication in various fields. Attempting to migrate to different countries for job opportunities, one needs to learn English contents.	Utilizing English for Diverse Contexts		Situated Learning Theory
Impacts of Pedagogical Approaches in Various Fields on Affecting Behavior	Applying and using the language in real-world situations Learning and studying English for one's	Techniques for Engaging		

During the Learning Process	profession Fostering interaction and speaking through always utilizing the language in the class discussion Changing the teaching style and converting to an engaging learning context in order not to be boring Innovating teaching methods for motivating students to have a positive attitude Implementing instructional materials that utilize the English language and strategizing in the teaching style Allowing students to commit errors in utilizing the language in the learning process Setting standards that align with the cognitive development of students in their learning progress Practicing oneself regularly for improving language skills Exposing oneself in various contexts where it utilizes English Allowing oneself to be mistaken in English grammar usage	Classroom Discussion Effective Mechanisms for Continuous Learning Constant Learning and Adaptation	Behaviorist Theory
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Learning English Language Takes Time and Effort. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion, with subcategories struggling with communication in the learning process and language practice with time and effort. The participants mentioned that they struggle to use English in communication and that it takes time and effort.

Struggles with communication in the learning process. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Participants from IDI and FGD said that they have struggles learning English for communication. These struggles can hinder the learning experience and make it harder to engage with the material or interact with others.

Similarly, learning English is difficult if you use it in communication when trying to effectively express your thoughts, ideas, or questions in an educational setting. English is a second language where students encounter challenges when it comes to learning in order to have good communication. Ms. Hopeful stated that:

“Lisod, legit lisod jud sya kay why po? English baya noh kang ginagamit sa communication niya kaduhang language pajud nato na dri sa pilipinas maong lisod ug di nimo tun-an.” (IDI-05)

(Difficult, it is really difficult because why? English is the language used in communication, it is our second language here in the Philippines, that is why it is difficult and hard to learn.)

To add, Ms. Empowered finds it difficult to understand English concepts but is striving to improve with time and effort. Students are facing challenges in comprehending and grasping various aspects of the English language. With this, they recognize that improvement requires consistent effort, practice, and dedication over time. She stated that:

“So, as nonboard student noh, gina consider jud nako ang English as a language to learn nga lisod kaayo tun-an and it really needs time and effort nga dapat imoha ibutang diraa para ma develop jud imohang English proficiency.” (IDI-04)

(So, as a non-board student, you know, I really consider English as a language to learn that is very difficult to study, and it really requires time and effort that you should invest in order to truly develop your English proficiency.)

Language practice with time and effort. This is the second code for the first probed issue. Participants stated that they need time and effort to learn English or gain proficiency in English to achieve communication, which leads to some opportunities for students to cultivate understanding of the language.

In that sense, English is considered the second language and is often used as a medium of communication. In such contexts, learning English becomes crucial for effective communication, whether it’s for social interactions, education, or professional purposes. Mr. Motivated said that:

“Sa pagtoon nako sa English although there are times na difficult siya, lisod siya but for me learning in English is that communication.” (FGD-01)

(In my study of English, although there are times when it is difficult, challenging, but for me, learning in English is all about communication.)

Additionally, students will gain proficiency in English through language practice, time, and effort, which will lead to numerous opportunities. One of those is that if they are implemented abroad and require work, it is an advantage since English is useful when it comes to communicating. As Ms. Eager mentioned that:

“Akong maingon rajud is need nato ma learn ang English, why? because aron masanay ug ma hawd ta kay para inig abot sa panahon if ma implement ta mag abroad or requirement sa atoang work puhon maybe English is very useful in communicating foreigners and partnerships diba. So nagamit imong natun-an wala siya nabasura lang. So that’s it.” (IDI-01)

(What I can only say is, we need to learn English, why? Because to get used to it and become proficient, so when the time comes, if we are implemented to go abroad or it is a requirement for our future work, maybe English is very useful in communicating with foreigners and partnerships, right? So, you can use what you have learned, it would not just go to waste. So that is it.)

Moreover, Ms. Shy highlighted the importance of giving the time and effort required to learn English effectively because of being burdened. The burden of learning English can also be seen as an opportunity for personal growth and development. By investing time and effort into learning English, one can enhance their communication skills, broaden their perspectives, and open up new opportunities for students. She said that:

“It is difficult and burdened but we gave time and effort just to learn English.” (FGD-05)

Exposure to language Use and Enhance One’s Learning. The second essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion have two codes/ category namely English proficiency for better opportunities and language immersion simulation methods for professional development. The participants mentioned that they are immersing themselves in an environment where the language is actively spoken and has advantages and opportunities.

English proficiency for better opportunities. This is the first code for the second probed issue. The participants from IDI and FGD stated that developing English proficiency can value the importance of English for the reason that it can be used in career advancement or international communication.

Similarly, Ms. Concerned valued the benefits of learning English for better opportunities. The advantages of being proficient can unlock opportunities, such as career opportunities or jobs where some require you to use English, especially to work internationally. She stated that:

“Ang mga non-board maka beneficial especially sa akoa like sa career opportunities or mga jobs na makuha puhon where some sa mga trabaho is naga require ug English language skills. Like anang mga call center diba so katong mga non-board program students who are proficient in English wakoy labot ato ha, have opportunity na maka work in internationally na mga companies or di kaya mag earn ug units sa education tas hawd kayo sa English, pwede ka mahimong English tutor”. (IDI-03)

(Non-board individuals can benefit, especially like me, in terms of career opportunities or jobs that may require English language skills. For example, in call centers, right? So, non-board program students who are proficient in English, like me, have the opportunity to work in international companies or even earn education units with a strong English background. You can even become an English tutor.)

Additionally, to attempt to go abroad or migrate to indifferent countries for job opportunities and to communicate effectively with people, students need to acquire English language skills in order to increase their chances of finding employment in foreign countries. As Ms. Calm stated that:

“Dapat nato tun-an ang English para dili nata maglisod especially if gusto ka mag-abroad dili naka maglisod ug communicate sa ubang tao.” (FGD-04)

(We should learn English so that we would not struggle, especially if we want to go abroad. You would not have a hard time communicating with other people.)

Furthermore, English has become a global language of communication, and its widespread use allows professionals and students from diverse backgrounds and cultures to connect and work in various fields. Ms. Concerned said that:

“Kinahanglan nato maglearn ug English para sa communication kay I know man gud na ang English is the most widely used language for communication in various fields, like anang mga businesses, education, and travel diay, sa laing nasud mga in ana. Knowing that ang English gina allow ang usa ka individuals to effectively communicate with people from different countries and cultures.” (IDI-04)

(We need to learn English for communication because I know that English is the most widely used language for communication in various fields, like businesses, education, and travel, in other countries and such. Knowing that English allows an individual to effectively communicate with people from different countries and cultures.)

Utilizing English for Diverse Contexts. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants stated that using and learning

English in real-world situations or in one's profession. It involves creating simulated environments or scenarios where individuals can practice and develop their language skills in a realistic and practical manner.

In the sense, Ms. Empowered recognizes the importance of learning English for the reason that it can be used and applied in real-world situations. This factor wanted students to use English in various contexts where it was needed in communication or jobs. Students are able to navigate real-life situations with ease and successfully interact with native speakers. She affirmed that:

“As non-board student noh, kailangan jud nato magtoon ug English language kay magamit man nato na siya in real-world situations nga kanang mag apply tag trabaho wherein naga required jud sila ug kanang personnel or trabahante nga hawud sa English.” (IDI-04)

(As a non-board student, it is really necessary for us to learn the English language because we can actually use it in real-world situations, like when we apply for jobs where they really require personnel or employees who are proficient in English.)

Lastly, learning English for one's profession is important. Acquiring English language skills specifically tailored to meet the demands and requirements of a particular occupation or career field. English proficiency for one's profession focuses on developing effective communication skills within a professional setting. As Mr. Motivated mentioned that:

“Kinahanglan siya magtoon kog English for my profession as a public administration.” (FGD-01)

(I need to learn English for my profession as a public administration.)

Constant Practice Using the Language Makes One Proficient in Language Use. This is another theme that emerged from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview and focus group discussion with codes strategies and methods for interactive class discussion, effective mechanisms for continually learning English for better behavior and constant learning and adaptation. The participants mentioned that learning methods or learning styles help them improve their positive attitude and become proficient in the language.

Techniques for engaging classroom discussion. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants stated that the use of the teaching style or teaching methods of teachers converts into interactive classroom discussion and motivates students to learn the language.

Similarly, one of the strategies teachers use to enhance their students learning of the language is to critical thinking and communication skills and vocabulary enhance. With this, students will be able to practice creating an environment that is consistently used as the primary language of communication during classroom interactions and discussions. Ms. Eager suggested that:

“Akoang ma suggest or ma recommend sa mga language teachers kay maggamit ug mga materials na maka enhance samo or di kaya kanang always nalang ipa utilize samo ang English through interacting or speaking. Kay para kana na way maynalang ma enhance ang amoang English ug makatoon ug maayo.” (IDI-01)

(My suggestion or recommendation to language teachers is to use materials that can enhance our English skills or to always utilize English through interactive and speaking activities. This way, our English can be improved and we can learn effectively.)

Moreover, teachers have different teaching strategies in classroom contexts that do not make it harder for the students to grasp the contents and concepts of the English language. Students wanted the teaching style of the teachers to not be boring to enhance their learning process. As Ms. Compassionate mentioned that:

“Okay so, ang akoang ma suggest no or recommendation sa ano sa language teachers, kay pangita mo ug way kanang ang inyohang teaching style dili boring, why? Daghan kay nagakoan ana, na boring ang English. Actually, ang enjoyment sapag learn ug English is depending lang siya sa pagkoan, how the teacher teach if ever mura siyag patay na nagtudlo din wala jud na siya. An affective teacher gains a bright students.” (IDI-02)

(So, my suggestion or recommendation to language teachers is to find a way to make their teaching style not boring. Why? Because many students find English boring. Actually, the enjoyment of learning English depends on how it is taught. If the teacher seems like they are not just going through the motions and not engaged, it can really affect the students' enthusiasm. An effective teacher inspires bright students.)

To add, Ms. Hopeful is emphasizing the importance of using strategies in the classroom discussion about English. Such teaching methods, which incorporate students to participate actively in the learning process. This method can help students enhance their positive attitude while learning the English language. Ms. Hopeful mentioned that:

“I guess akoang ma suggest ug ma recommend isa rajud kanang teaching methods gud daw sa mga teacher I think maayo sad ni na way para sa mga language teacher.” (IDI-05)

(I guess my suggestion and recommendation is really just that, for teachers to consider using effective teaching methods. I think this is also a good way for language teachers.)

Effective mechanisms for continuous learning. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Students learn English for better

behavior, which means using the English language as a tool to improve their communication skills, cultural understanding, and overall behavior. Effective mechanism for continuously learning for better behavior. Such as allowing students to commit errors or mistakes and setting standards and instructional materials.

Similarly, for continually learning better behavior and allowing students to commit errors or mistakes, it emphasizes creating an environment where students feel comfortable making mistakes while using the language since they are not specialized in the language. Recognizes that errors are a natural part of learning the language and provides a safe space for students to experiment, take risks, and learn from their mistakes. Ms. Empowered said that:

“So akong ma recommend sa mga English instructors noh na para effective ang students teacher learning process kay e-allow sa mga English teachers nga mamali jud ang mga students kay non-board gani sila so it means dili sila specialized ana nga field. So, para ma motivates sila maka build silag positive attitudes in learning English language.” (IDI-04)

(My recommendation to English instructors is that in order for the student-teacher learning process to be effective, English teachers should allow students to make mistakes because they are not experts in that field in order to motivate and build positive attitudes toward learning English.)

Additionally, setting standards in English learning means establishing clear expectations and criteria for what students should know and be able to do at each stage of their language development. Teachers establish expectations and goals that are appropriate for the student’s cognitive abilities, not too high or too low, but moderate, where it fits the students’ needs when learning the English language. As Mr.

Motivated stated that:

“Siguro akong ma recommend sa mga teachers or English teachers they set standards na dili kaayo makoang ang mga bata when it comes learning English and they implement sa mga strategies in order para dali ra makatoon ang mga bata. And also, when it comes in learning English dili kaayo siya long duration it’s because according to psychologist, 5-10 minutes lang yata ang duration sa mga bata sa pagtoon.” (FGD-01)

(I would recommend to teachers or English teachers to set standards that are not too overwhelming for children when it comes to learning English and to implement strategies that make it easy for children to learn. Additionally, when it comes to learning English, it should not be for a long duration because according to psychologists, children’s attention span for learning is only around 5-10 minutes.)

Moreover, instructional materials, or resources, are tools that educators use to facilitate learning and instruction in the classroom. This approach aims to immerse students in the English language and provide them with opportunities to practice and develop their language skills. As Ms. Concerned mentioned that:

“Kadungog ko ana sa mga ano education department anang about instructional materials. Siguro, importante ang mga instruction materials na ma e recommends nako sa mga language teacher’s kay maka help mn gud ni sya in learning English and ma enhance nato ang pag speak ug English bisan asa.” (IDI-03)

(I have heard about that from the education department regarding instructional materials. Perhaps, it is important for me to recommend instructional materials to language teachers because it can really help in learning English and enhance our English-speaking skills anywhere.)

Constant learning and adaptation. This is the third code for the third probed issue. The participants from IDI and FGD stated that they were adjusting and modifying one’s approach to learning the English language in order to meet the needs, challenges, and goals. It involves allowing oneself to be mistaken, practicing regularly, exposing oneself in various contexts, and giving effort to continuously improve your English language skills and adapt to the evolving demands of language learning.

Similarly, making mistakes is a part of learning, especially in the English language. Allowing oneself to be mistaken in English grammar or anything makes students open to making mistakes while learning the language. Students adopt a positive attitude towards mistakes and view them as learning opportunities rather than failures. Ms. Hopeful suggested that:

“As my experience, akoang ma suggest sa akoang fellow non-board student’s kay do not be afraid to make mistake means kanang ug maglearn kag English di man jud ingon perfect or hawud dayon, it takes time to learn, the longer we take the worth we achieve.” (IDI-05)

(Based on my experience, my suggestion to my fellow non-board students is do not be afraid to make mistakes. It means that when you are learning English, it does not have to be perfect or fluent right away. It takes time to learn, and the longer we take, the more progress we can achieve.)

Additionally, Ms. Concerned practicing regularly to improve English language skills and constant learning is that students engage in consistent and intentional activities to enhance one’s proficiency in the language. Students keep on practicing to improve various language components such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing. She stated that:

“Siguro akoang ma suggest ra kay always practicely regularly lang jud like sako sauna pero kron naondang kay sa ka busy, but practice daw makes perfect but siguro ug sige tag practice ug toon is ma conquered mn jud nato atoang goals ang improvement the way maglears ta English, importante sad baya ang English noh. Maong always practice rajud.” (IDI-03)

(I would suggest that you always practice regularly, just like what I used to do before, but I understand that things have changed due to being busy. However, practice makes perfect, and if we consistently practice and strive to improve, we can achieve our English learning goals. English is also important, so it is crucial to always practice.)

Lastly, exposing oneself to various contexts where English is utilized actively seeks out opportunities to engage with the language in different real-life situations. Students immerse themselves in environments where English is spoken or used as a means of communication. As Ms. Empowered said that:

“Ang akoang masuggest sa akoang fellow students noh nga ga encounter ug difficulties in learning English kay e-expound ilahang vocabulary, expose ang sarili sa mga context or sitwasyon nga ga utilize ug English kay diraa na way ma improve sila sa ilahang English proficiency.” (IDI-04)

(My suggestion to my fellow students who encounter difficulties in learning English is to expand their vocabulary and expose themselves to contexts or situations where English is used. This is where they can improve their English proficiency.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the attitudes towards English language learning of non-board program students in a local college carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The fifth research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 5 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in preceding columns.

Attitude Towards English Language Learning. The result showed that the quantitative phase and qualitative phase of the study converged when its findings and results were merged. The item 1 about the emotional category, I feel proud when studying English language which is rated as high had the same result with the qualitative finding on the codes worthwhile and satisfaction with the core ideas A gratifying sense of worth derives from investing time and effort, leading to significant improvements. Additionally, the items 2 and 4, I feel excited when I communicate in English with others and I feel good when studying foreign languages like English is enjoyable, both rated as high, the results were consistent with the qualitative codes worthwhile and satisfaction with the core ideas A satisfying and exciting feeling makes learning easier and challenging and feeling happy and fulfilled while learning English where students gain knowledge. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Table 8. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Finding</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Attitudes Towards English Language Learning	From table 2 on the level of attitudes towards English language learning in terms of emotional item 1 I feel proud when studying English language (M=4.14), item 2 I feel excited when I communicate in English with others (M=3.82) and item 4 I feel good when studying foreign languages like English is enjoyable (M=3.88), these are rated as high.	Table 4.1 on the lived experiences of non-board program students with regards to their attitude towards English language learning highlight the code worthwhile and satisfaction with the core ideas A gratifying sense of worth derives from investing time and effort, leading to significant improvements, A satisfying and exciting feeling makes learning easier and challenging and feeling happy and fulfilled while learning English, where students gain knowledge.	Merging – Converging	Students' emotional feelings when learning the English language result in positive attitudes.
	Table 2 on behavioral item 1 I think speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried (M=3.73) which is rated as high.	From table 4.1 on the lived experiences of non-board program students with regards to their attitude towards English language learning highlight the code psychological barrier breakdown with the core ideas Feeling bad about learning English and acquiring a negative attitude.	Merging – Converging	Non-board programs experiencing barrier breakdowns hamper the learning process.
	From table 2 on the level of attitudes towards English language learning	Table 4.2 on the coping mechanisms of non-board program students with regards	Merging – Converging	Students cope with challenges by being

in terms of behavioral item 2 I ponder studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends (M=3.49), item 5 I hear a student in my class speaking English well, I like to practice speaking with him/her (M=3.78) with both high descriptive equivalents.	to their attitudes towards English language learning highlight the code Promoting Effective Collaboration with others while Learning with the core ideas Valuing the importance of seeking support from peers and friends and asking for help from the teacher or a fellow student.	more attentive in class discussion.
From the table 2 on cognitive item 1 I believe studying English is important because it will make me more educated (M=4.44), item 5 I feel that studying English helps me get new information that I can link to my previous knowledge (M=4.21), both of these rated as very high and high.	Table 4.3 the insights shared of non-board program students with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning highlight the code Utilizing English for Diverse Contexts with the core ideas Applying and using the language in real-world situations.	Merging – Converging Participants keep learning for professional development improvements and are open to learning more.

Moreover, in the quantitative phase, the specific item on the behavioral, I think speaking English anywhere makes me feel worried rated as high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, on the codes psychological barriers breakdown with the core ideas Feeling bad about learning English and acquiring a negative attitude. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Further, in the quantitative phase, on behavioral about I ponder studying English helps me to have good relationships with friends and I hear a student in my

class speaking English well, I like to practice speaking with him/her are rated both as high. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is under on the code promoting effective collaboration with others while learning with the core ideas valuing the importance of seeking support from peers and friends and asking for help from the teacher or a fellow student who has better understanding of the language. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Moreover, the specific items on behavioral, I like to give opinions during English lessons and I am able to make myself pay attention during studying English both rated as high. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the code of Developing an Optimistic Mindset for Ongoing English Learning with the core ideas Building a positive attitude helps one understand concepts while honing language learning skills and considering positive attitudes as motivation in the development of English competency. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

In addition, the specific items on cognitive, I believe studying English is important because it will make me more educated rated as very high. Also, I feel that studying English helps me get new information that I can link to my previous knowledge is rated as very high. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, on the code utilizing English for diverse contexts with the core ideas applying and using the language in real-world situations. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The level of attitude towards English language learning of non-board program students is high. This indicates that the non-board program students show positive attitude towards learning English. It is also concluded that students have self-confidence in engaging English and they enjoyed in learning the language which illustrates their positive emotions towards English language learning. Students were actively participating, shows interest and motivation in learning the English language which indicates their positive behavior towards English language learning. Also, students were able to see the value and benefits that can be acquire in learning English and it motivates them to learn English language which indicates their positive cognition towards learning the language. Furthermore, positive attitude of students towards English language learning helps them to be competent in the language.

The lived experiences of non-board program students had determined their attitude towards learning English specifically the positive and negative attitude, as well as the reasons why they have that kind of attitude. The result also shows that, having positive attitude towards learning English help students in learning the language, improves their performance and enable them to be good in English language. However, students who have negative attitude towards English language learning was having a hard time in learning the language. The qualitative data was thematically analyzed using responses obtained from conducting in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). The findings provided additional insights into the students' perspective regarding their experiences and challenges faced attitudes towards English language learning. Qualitatively, non-board program students have been experiencing different situations which contribute to the way how attitude affected they're towards English language. The following themes were emerged: experiencing negative attitude on language learning and use, having difficulty in understanding and using the language

effectively, overcoming psychological barriers to achieve fulfillment and satisfaction, and encountering difficulty in using the language as medium of communication and instruction classroom participation.

From the participants responses, other themes are identified which show the coping mechanisms shared of non-board program students with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning. The following are the themes: applying various techniques to discover and improve language learning and use, promoting effective collaboration and social learning, cultivating optimism for lifelong language learning and proficiency, and empowering learning through customized interactive resources.

Furthermore, from the respondent's responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of non-board program students with regards to their attitudes towards English language learning. The following are the themes: learning English language takes time and effort, exposure to language use and enhance one's learning, and constant practice using the language makes one proficient in language use.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of how students' attitudes towards learning English affect them, the responses were analyzed thematically to validate the study's quantitative findings. The results from both phases are combined in accordance with the nature plan. The level of attitudes towards English language learning and the quantitative findings indicate that they align with the data obtained during the qualitative stage. The quantitative and qualitative results both validate that despite of the attitudes in learning English also have negative side effects, the positive effects and benefits of attitudes towards English language learning where much more significant.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the level of attitude towards English language learning of non-board program students is high, which indicates that students have positive attitude towards learning English. It is recommended that students should expose their self-more on learning materials, encourage active participation in English language activities, and incorporate multimedia resources in their learning process not just to maintain the positive attitude of students towards English language learning but to enhance/improve it even more. Parents are also recommended to encourage their children to have or maintain a positive attitude towards learning English for they are the most influential person for their children.

Out of the result covered, the non-board program has experienced difficulties using English effectively and a negative attitude towards language learning use, which indicates the negative attitude of students towards English language learning, and it is recommended that teachers should use a variety of teaching methods to cater to their different learning styles and preferences to make their learning more engaging and interesting and encourage students' self-reflection and self-assessment to help students improve their skills in the language. Furthermore, if future researchers become intrigued by the phenomena being studied, it is advisable that they not restrict their inquiries to only the experiences of non-board program students to gather more relevant information that can be connected to the attitude of students towards learning English language.

Furthermore, during the coping mechanism phase among non-board program students, with regards to the barriers to improving their attitudes toward the English language, this may assist students in addressing the problems and difficulties that they encountered during the learning process. Learning can be tailored and extended outside of the classroom by leveraging resources that use many languages and cater to students' variances in attitudes about the English language. In addition, collaborating and sustaining connections with peers and administrators are factors of good learning. Learning should be enjoyable, and students should not be put under any pressure to appreciate the beauty of learning in a supportive and inclusive environment.

Consequently, the shared insight of non-board program students with regards to their attitudes towards the English language may help them to address their learning needs. Furthermore, having the viewpoints and understanding may help students refine their set of attitudes toward the language. This may allow learners to make more informed judgments and adjust their specific demands to their preferences in order to learn. Allowing students to make mistakes in their learning process, especially using English as the means of communication. By embracing their mistakes, students were able to motivate and have positive attitudes toward the English language learning. In addition, the researcher wanted to recommend that the constant practice of using the language and the utilization of this mechanism would help students be better at English and make one proficient in the language. Additionally, exposure to language use can enhance learning and enrich one's ability to become an effective learner and user of the English language.

Since the result shows a diverging and converging integration, which indicates that there are students who have a positive attitude towards learning English and there are students who have a negative attitude towards learning English. So, I therefore recommend that the administrators of the school formulate ways to turn this negative attitude towards learning English into a positive one.

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